

Minor Actinide and Plutonium Generation in the SMART 100 Reactor

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ABSTRACT

It is expected that Integral Pressurized Water Reactors will behave similarly to large PWRs, and the backend strategy followed to date for large reactors is applicable to open and partially closed fuel cycles, but confirmatory analysis must be performed. This study aims to assess the behavior of the SMART-100 reactor by simulating its operation and by finding the Plutonium and MA produced during the operational life of the fuel assemblies. As a starting point, an equilibrium core for the SMART-100 reactor is designed, and the depleted fuel composition inventories are characterized. Results show that in an equilibrium cycle, 20 fuel assemblies can be kept for a second cycle, reducing the number of fresh assemblies to 37 per fuel reload every 30 months. Due to the loading strategy, 17 fuel assemblies have a burnup of around 25 GWd/MT, showing a 78% share of fissile plutonium, and the other 20 fuel assemblies have a burnup of around 43 GWd/MT with a similar behavior to standard depleted PWR fuel assemblies, around 70% share of fissile plutonium. The production of MA exhibits behavior very different from that of standard depleted PWR fuel assemblies from large reactors. Further investigation is needed to learn about these differences in MA generation.

Keywords: Small Modular Reactor, Minor Actinide, Plutonium, Integral PWR

1. INTRODUCTION

Small modular reactors promise to be an alternative for providing electricity capacity to meet stated demand progressively, with smaller up-front investment and shorter time to deployment than large reactors. More than 80 SMRs have been proposed to date, at various stages of development. They are grouped into four technologies: light-water reactors (land- and marine-based), gas-cooled reactors, molten-salt reactors, and liquid-metal fast-neutron reactors [1]. Light water reactors are mostly integral PWRs (iPWRs). They are based on PWR technology with new engineering development.

Among these iPWRs are: the KLT-70 nuclear reactor, which is in operation in Russia, the ACP-100 that is being deployed in China, the VOYGR has already been certified in the USA, and the SMART-100 has a Standard Design Approval by the Republic of Korea regulatory body and could be deployed in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Integral Pressurized Water Reactors are a proven technology that could leverage experience already gained in large water reactors; however, iPWRs will use shorter fuel assemblies and have cores

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composed of fewer fuel assemblies. These differences could affect SMRs' depleted-fuel composition inventory; confirmatory analysis is required to characterize depleted fuel from iPWRs.

It is expected that iPWRs will behave similarly to large PWRs, and the backend strategy followed to date for large reactors is applicable to open and closed fuel cycles. This study aims to assess the behavior of the SMART-100 reactor by simulating its operation and by finding the plutonium and MA produced during the operational life of the fuel assemblies.

The SMART-100 core consists of 57 fuel assemblies; they are standard 17x17 fuel assemblies, but differ from those in large reactors in height. There is no anticipated information on the inventories of depleted fuel at the end of their operational life; this will be the primary outcome of the analysis to learn about Pu and MA inventories.

2. SMART-100 REACTOR

The SMART-100 reactor (System-integrated Modular Advanced Reactor) is an integrated pressurized water reactor with a 365 MW thermal capacity, a core composed of 57 standard 17x17 PWR fuel assemblies measuring 2.00 m in height. It is considered to operate in 30-month cycles with a 60-year lifetime [2, 3].

2.1. Reactor Core

The initial core consists of 6 batches: 4 with 4.88 w/o uranium enrichment and differing numbers of gadolinium rods, and 2 with 2.82 w/o uranium enrichment and differing numbers of gadolinium rods [4]. Table I shows the main characteristics of this reactor, and Figure 1 shows the quarter-core fuel assembly arrangement.

Table I. SMART-100 reactor specifications [2-4].

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Reactor thermal capacity MW _{th}	365	Core coolant inlet temperature C	295.7
Power plant electrical capacity MW _e	110	Core coolant outlet temperature C	323
Equivalent core diameter (m)	1.8316	Active core height (m)	2
Rated power density kW/l	69.26	Number of fuel assemblies	57
Specific power kW/kU	23.079	Lattice geometry	Square
Reactor operating pressure (MPa)	15	Average linear heat rate kW/m	12.13
Primary coolant flow rate (kg/s)	2311	Fuel cycle length	898.5 EFPD 22.3 GWd/Mt

					Type	Burnt	Assemblies	U-235 enrichment	Gd rods	Gd enrichment
			A0	B0	A	0	8	4.88	4	8.00
		B0	D0	C0	B	0	12	4.88	8	8.00
	B0	D0	E0	F0	C	0	4	4.88	24	8.00
A0	D0	E0	F0	E0	D	0	12	4.88	20	8.00
B0	C0	F0	E0	F0	E	0	12	2.82	8	8.00
					F	0	9	2.82	12	8.00

Figure 1. Fuel loading pattern for the initial cycle (1/4 core).2.82

2.2. Equilibrium core

The initial core is modeled using the Core Management System (CMS). CASMO-4, which uses a 70-group library based on ENDF/B-IV [4]. This code generates nuclear data for the different fuel assemblies considered, and SIMULATE-3 [5] is used to model and simulate the core's operation to verify the initial core cycle length. The results show the core's cycle length of 30 months (898.5 EFPD).

To determine the equilibrium cycle, several tests were performed to determine the maximum number of fuel assemblies that could be used in a second cycle to produce a cycle of the same length as the initial cycle. Results show that 20 fuel assemblies of types A and B can be used for a second cycle, and 37 fresh fuel assemblies are needed from types A, B, C, and D. The configuration of this equilibrium cycle is given in Figure 2.

					Type	Burnt	Burnup GWd/t	Assemblies	U-235 enrichment	Gd rods	Gd enrichment
			A0	B0	A	0	0	8	4.88	4	8.00
		B0	D0	C0	B	0	0	12	4.88	8	8.00
	B0	D0	A1	B1	C	0	0	5	4.88	24	8.00
A0	D0	A1	B1	B1	D	0	0	12	4.88	20	8.00
B0	C0	B1	B1	C0	A	1	16.09	8	4.88	4	8.00
					B	1	18.60	12	4.88	8	8.00

Figure 2. Fuel loading pattern for the equilibrium cycle (1/4 core).

3. RESULTS

An equilibrium core that achieves the same burnup as the initial core was designed, with a cycle length of 898.5 MWd/Mt (898.5 EFPD); it will deliver energy for a 30-month cycle, with 37 fresh fuel assemblies replaced and 20 used for a second cycle. The configuration of this second cycle is maintained, and subsequent cycles are simulated to ensure the same cycle length and to achieve the boron concentration in the equilibrium cycle. Figure 3 shows that this occurs at the fourth cycle.

Figure 3. Boron concentration performance to get the equilibrium cycle length.

Figure 4 shows the U-235 enrichment distribution, burnup, and gadolinium content for the initial core with only fresh fuel, and for the equilibrium cycle using 20 fuel assemblies in a second operation cycle. All the fresh fuel has a 4.88 w/o U-235 uranium enrichment for UO_2 rods, and the central fuel assembly is also a fresh fuel assembly.

The difference shown with U-235 enrichment is due to the different number of gadolinium rods used in the fuel assemblies. In addition, the 20 fuel assemblies for a second cycle show that gadolinium has been absorbed in the first cycle.

Fuel assemblies at discharge will not get the same burnup and the plutonium and minor actinide produced will be different, Table II shows plutonium content of the four types of assembly discharged with their corresponding final U-235 enrichment and its average burnup per fuel assembly, and for comparison is given the plutonium vector provided by the International Atomic Energy Agency for light water reactors at a 68.9 GWd/Mt [6].

In addition, Figure 5 shows the depletion chain used in CASMO-4 to report Pu and MA generation. As expected, there is a higher content of plutonium isotopes at higher burnup. The plutonium isotopes show changes with discharge burnup; for assembly types C0 and D0, with burnups of 26.692 and 24.560 GWd/Mt, respectively. They have a higher Pu-239 content, around 68%. It is due to a higher amount of U-235 and U-238, which are the precursors of Pu-239.

Figure 4. Fissile enrichment and gadolinium distribution for initial and equilibrium cores

Meanwhile, for assembly types A1 and B1, which have higher burnup 41.062 and 43.060 GWd/Mt, respectively. The amounts of U-235 and U-238 are lower, resulting in a decrease in the Pu-239 share to around 57%. As burnup increases, U-235 and U-238 decrease, reducing Pu-239 generation. The plutonium vector provided by the International Atomic Energy Agency [6] shows a 60.20% share of

Pu-239 at 68.9 GWd/Mt, which does not follow the decreasing trend observed in the SMART-100 reactor fuel assemblies. It could be because the PWR has a specific power of around 37.8 kW/kgU and a core power density of around 100 kW/l, compared with the SMART-100 reactor's particular power of 23.79 kW/kgU and core power density of 69.26 kW/l.

Table II. Plutonium isotopes from depleted fuel in the SMART-100 reactor and the plutonium vector provided by the IAEA, for comparison.

Type	U-235 w/o Final Enrichment	Burnup GWd/MT	Pu-238 g	Pu-239 g	Pu-240 g	Pu-241 g	Pu-242 g
C0	1.987	26.692	23.598 1.12%	1402.542 66.62%	392.958 18.66%	235.467 11.18%	50.787 2.41%
D0	2.155	24.561	18.204 0.91%	1369.168 68.69%	356.159 17.87%	209.455 10.51%	40.263 2.02%
A1	1.298	41.062	63.730 2.40%	1526.920 57.39%	573.889 21.57%	365.555 13.74%	130.694 4.91%
B1	1.185	43.060	71.033 2.61%	1525.477 56.00%	599.687 22.01%	381.854 14.02%	146.155 5.37%
Typical Pu Vector for PWR at 68.9 GWd/Mt [6]			1.50%	60.20%	24.50%	8.80%	5.00%

Table III. Minor actinide from depleted fuel in the SMART-100 reactor and typical MA vectors from depleted PWR fuel assemblies.

Type	Np-237 g	Am-241 g	Cm-244 g	Sum g
C0	87.395 88.69%	9.664 9.81%	1.477 1.50%	98.536
D0	78.002 89.56%	8.114 9.32%	0.977 1.12%	87.092
A1	154.384 84.44%	18.799 10.28%	9.652 5.28%	182.834
B1	162.761 83.60%	19.952 10.25%	11.972 6.15%	194.685
Typical MA Vector for PWR at 33GWd/t	64.07%	30.10%	5.83%	
Typical MA Vector for PWR at 45GWd/t	57.88%	37.41%	4.71%	

Figure 5. CASMO-4 depletion chain used to report Pu and MA generation

For minor actinides, only Np-237, Am-241, and Cm-244 are shown, because Np-239 and Cm-242 decay away in less than a half-year. Furthermore, Am-242m and Cm-243 each have a share of 0.0001 w/0 in the depleted fuel, with their contributions negligible, and Am-243 is not shown because CASMO-4 does not report it. Table III shows the Np-237, Am-241, and Cm-244 shares per fuel assembly and two reference Np-237, Am-241, and Cm-244 vectors for PWR fuel assemblies with burnups of 33 GWd/MT and 45 GWd/MT [7] to compare the results obtained for the discharged fuel assemblies of the SMART-100 reactor. Results show a very different behavior of Np-237, Am-241, and Cm-244 from depleted fuel in the SMART-100 reactor compared with those reported in the reference.

There is a higher share of Np-237 around 84% for fuel assembly types A1 and B1, and around 89% for assembly types C0 and D0. As mentioned previously, in the SMART-100 reactor at lower burnup, there is a higher amount of U-235 and U-238, which are precursors to Np-237 (see Figure 5). As burnup increases, precursors decrease, reducing the Np-237 share.

For Am-241 production, the generation is around 10% across all fuel assembly types, compared with 30.10% and 37.41% shown in the reference PWR fuel assemblies. Cm-244 shows a lower share – around 1.5% – for assembly types C0 and D0. The share is comparable to that of the reference PWR fuel assemblies and of the assembly types A1 and B1. However, this may be circumstantial, as SMART-100 fuel assemblies are exposed to different core characteristics than those reported for the PWR reference vectors. Table IV shows the fast and thermal fluxes at the beginning of the cycle (BOC) and at the end of the cycle (EOC) for a typical PWR [8] and the SMART-100 reactor.

Table IV. Fast and thermal fluxes at BOC and EOC.

	PWR		SMART	
	BOC	EOC	BOC	EOC
Fast Flux (1×10^{14} n/cm ² -s)	3.116	3.241	1.875	1.875
Thermal Flux (1×10^{14} n/cm ² -s)	0.413	0.511	0.215	0.262

Additional investigation is needed to understand these differences in MA generation and their implications, and to determine alternative backend strategies that account for the recycling of plutonium and MA.

4. CONCLUSIONS

According to the proposed initial core loading for the SMART-100 reactor, an equilibrium core that achieves the same cycle length as the initial core was designed. In this equilibrium core, twenty fuel assemblies can be kept for a second cycle, reducing the number of fresh assemblies to 37 per fuel reload every 30 months.

Due to the fuel reloading strategy followed, 17 fuel assemblies have lower burnups, around 25 GWd/MT, showing a higher share of fissile plutonium than the other 20 fuel assemblies, which have burnups around 43 GWd/MT and exhibit behavior similar to standard depleted PWR fuel assemblies.

Production of MA shows a very different behavior from that of standard depleted PWR fuel assemblies, with a higher share of Np-237 –around 80% compared to around 60% –and a lower share of Cm-244: around 5% for assembly types C0 and D0, and similar for assembly types A1 and B1. These differences are due to different environments. PWR has a specific power of around 37.8 kW/kgU and a core power density of around 100 kW/l, compared with the SMART-100 reactor's particular power of 23.79 kW/kgU and a core power density of 69.26 kW/l.

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